

Co-Operatives in India

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Abstract

One of the most effective and efficient tool for fighting against all odds is togetherness; and especially in a country like India, where a large number of people are socio-economically backward, a sense of collective effort is desirable to enhance the livelihood of the marginalised. Forming Co-Operatives is one of the most tested and trusted tool to bring the homogeneous people closer and to prosper together by confronting the challenges. Although not being an indigenous concept, and introduced by the British rulers, in India the co-operative movement has taken its shape in a positive direction. The collective approach for development is a boost to the direction towards socio-economic progress. This article tries to reflect a few perspectives of co-operatives in India and it also tries to find out the course of direction since its inception in this country.

Keywords: Co-Operative, Agricultural Co-Operatives, Marketing Co-Operatives, Co-Operative credit Societies, Co-Operative Banks.

Introduction

The history of co-operatives in India is more than a century old. It has changes its course since inception with the change of time. Also, its intensity of evolution has magnified many fold especially after the Independence.

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The initiative taken by Lord Curzon has flourished quite evidently in this country so that it has become a handy tool for economic upliftment of many clusters with common opportunities and threats. Around the globe, modern co-operatives have evolved for more than two centuries. Co-Operative institutions exist all round the world providing essential services. In many Third World countries, co-operatives, such as credit unions and agricultural organizations, have been quite successful in helping people to provide for themselves where private and other corporate capitals do not find high profitability. Globally, co-operatives have been able to improve their position as powerful economic model of development. In some countries they are a sizeable force within the national economy.

Definition

Co-Operative Society was defined by C.R. Fay as follows : "A co-operative Society is an association for the purpose of Joint Trading, organising among the weak and conducted always in an unselfish spirit, on such terms that all are prepared to assume the duties of membership may share in its rewards in proportion to the degree in which they make use of their association." (Madan, 2007)

Historical Background of Indian Co-operatives: Pre-Independence

The co-operative movement in India started from agriculture and allied sectors. Towards the end of the 19th century, the problems of rural indebtedness and the consequent conditions of farmers created an environment for the MFIs and co-operative societies. The farmers generally found the concept of co-operative movement an attractive way for solving some problems like credit, inflow of inputs and marketing of agricultural produce. It was found that during the British rule, Nicholson, a British officer in

India, suggested introducing of “Raiffersen model”, a German model for agricultural credit co-operatives. As a follow-up of that recommendation, the first Co-operative Society Act of 1904 was passed and “Agricultural credit co-operative” were formed in many villages all over India under the patronage of the government. After this, co-operative got a separate identity under the provisions of the law; and henceforth every agricultural co-operative was registered under that Act. The 1904 Co-Operative Societies Act was replaced by 1912 Co-Operative Societies Act which provided formation of co-operative societies other than credit. Subsequently, a more comprehensive legislation called the Co-Operative Societies Act was enacted. This Act, provided for the creation of the post of registrar of co-operative societies and registration of co-operative societies for various purposes and audit.

Under the Montague-Chelmsford Reforms of 1919, cooperation became a provincial subject and the provinces were authorised to make their own co-operative laws. Under the Government of India Act, 1935, 'Co-Operatives' were treated as a provincial subject. It may be noted that under the Administrative Reforms Act (1919), for the first time, 'co-operatives' was made a provincial subject making each province responsible for co-operative development. The item “Co-Operative Societies” is a State Subject under entry No.32 of the State List of the Constitution of India¹.

Later, in 1942, the British Government enacted the Multi-Unit Co-Operative Societies Act, (1942) with an object to cover societies whose operations are extended to more than one state. The Indian freedom movement

gave birth to many initiatives and institutions in the post independence era in India and armed with an experience of 42 years in the working of Multi Unit Co-Operative Societies and the Multi-Unit Co-Operative Societies Act, 1942, the Central Government enacted a comprehensive Act known as Multi State Co-Operative Societies Act, (1984), modifying the Act of 1942. In order to cover Co-Operative Societies with membership from more than one province, the Government of India enacted the Multi-Unit Co-Operative Societies Act(1942). This Act was an enabling legislative instrument dealing with incorporation and winding up of co-operative societies having jurisdiction in more than one province. Later on the concept of national federations of co-operative societies came up in various functional areas and to regulate multistate co-operative societies as well as to consolidate the laws governing such co-operative societies, a comprehensive Central legislation was formed. Therefore, the Multi-State Co-Operative Societies Act(1984) was enacted by Parliament under Entry No. 44 of the Union List of the Constitution of India².

The process of Evolution of Co-Operatives: Post-Independence

After India attained Independence in August, 1947, co-operatives were regarded of great significance in removing poverty and speeding up socio-economic growth. As the concept of Planning got shape in India, co-operatives became an integral part of the Five Year Plans. As a result, they emerged as a salient feature in our Indian economy. In the First Five Year Plan, it was confirmed that the success of the Plan would be judged, along with other things, by the extent it was implemented through co-operatives. The All-India Rural Credit Survey Committee Report(1954) recommended that co-operative credit should be comprehensive and credit co-operative societies should expand their area

¹ Press Information Bureau, G. O. (n.d.). *Press Information Bureau, Govt. Of India*. Retrieved October 14, 2015, from Press Information Bureau, Govt. Of India: <http://www.pib.nic.in/feature/fe0299/f1202992.htm>
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² Ibid

of operation, so that rural people can have more savings and business of the co-operative societies proliferate. It also recommended that certain amount of share capital of the co-operatives should be held by the Government.

In view of these recommendations, different States initiated various schemes for the Co-Operative movement for organising large-size societies and provision of State partnership and assistance. During 1960s, the structure of co-operative societies was re-modulated.

Meanwhile, in 1958 the National Development Council (NDC) had recommended a national policy on co-operatives. The first Prime Minister of India, Jawaharlal Nehru was a strong believer of the co-operative movement, hence Five year Plans included focus on co-operatives.

Thus, the co-operative sector has been playing a distinct and significant role in the country's process of socio-economic development. There has been a substantial growth of this sector in diverse areas of the economy during the past few decades. The number of all types of co-operatives increased from 1.81 lakh in 1950-51 to 4.53 lakh in 1996-97. The total membership of co-operative societies increased from 1.55 crore to 20.45 crore during the same period. The co-operatives have been operating in various areas of the economy such as credit, production, processing, marketing, input distribution, housing, dairying and textiles. In some of the areas of their activities like dairying, urban banking and housing, sugar and handlooms, the co-operatives have achieved success to an extent but there are larger areas where they have not been so successful³.

Evidently, India, since the country's independence from Britain in 1947, has seen a

³ Ibid

huge growth in co-operative societies serving mainly the farming sector. For example, most of the sugar production in India takes place at mills owned by local co-operative societies. The members of the society include all farmers, small and large, supplying sugarcane to the mill. Over the last fifty years, the local sugar mills have played a crucial part in encouraging political participation and as a stepping stone for aspiring politicians.

Co-Operatives also play a great part in dairy marketing as well as banking. Co-Operative banks in India serve both the rural and urban societies. Just like the Sugar companies, these institutions serve as the power base for local politicians.

Verghese Kurien in his book "I too had a dream" details the problems, solutions and experiences he had in setting up and developing the dairy co-operative society now known as Amul⁴.

Types of Co-Operatives

There are numerous types of co-operatives. We can differentiate it into following types:

- **Producer co-operatives:** These are the co-operatives which process and market their members' products and services directly while others may also sell the input necessary to their members' economic activities. Examples: Agriculture co-operatives, pooling of equipment, advisory services, etc.
- **Multi-stakeholder co-operatives:** The members of these co-operatives are

⁴ Cited in WIKIPEDIA. (2014, September 10). *Cooperative movement in India*. Retrieved October 14, 2015, from WIKIPEDIA: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cooperative_movement_in_India

from different categories but they share a common interest in the organization. Examples: home care services, health services, community services, etc.

- Worker co-operatives: These co-operatives are operated by the members themselves like the owners of an enterprise. Examples: forestry, leisure, production and manufacturing, tourism, communications and marketing, etc.
- Worker-Shareholder co-operatives: These are incorporated co-operatives that hold partial ownership of the business in which the co-op's members are employed. Because of its share capital, the co-operative may participate in the management of the business and the workers may influence work organization. Examples: production and manufacturing, technology, etc.
- Consumer co-operatives: The members are provided with goods and services for their personal use. Examples: Food, credit unions, housing, insurance co-operatives, etc⁵.

Global view of Co-operative

In the 19th century in Europe the cooperative movement began, initially in Britain and France. The Shore Porters Society was one of the world's first cooperatives, established in Aberdeen in 1498. The Industrial Revolution transformed society and economy growth process and threatened the livelihoods of many workers. The first

⁵ COOPZONE. (n.d.). *Types of Co-operatives*. Retrieved November 25, 2015, from COOPZONE: http://coopzone.coop/en/coop_types

documented consumer cooperative, Fenwick weavers' society development, local weavers ,John Walker, moulded lime in the front room and started to sell at a discount in a barely furnished cottage, was established in 1769. In 1830, hundreds of cooperatives were successful initially, but most of the co-operatives were established in the early 19th century. In 1840, however, Lockhurst Lane Industrial Co-operative Society (founded in 1832 and now the Heart of England Co-operative Society) failed, but Galashiels and Hawick Co-operative Societies continued trading. Rochdale Equitable Pioneers Society developed and the modern co-operative movement was initiated on the basis of "Rochdale Principles". Financially, the credit union and Friedrich Wilhelm Raiffeisen (1864, rural) by Franz Hermann Schulze-Delitzsch (1852, urban), the first of its kind, was invented in Germany in the mid-19th century. Though chronologically before, Schulze-Delitzsch, Raiffeisen have been more influential over time –if you see the history of the credit union. In Britain, friendly societies, building societies, mutual savings banks and similar institutions started to form by then.

Some eminent personalities involved in world co-operative movement

Robert Owen: Robert Owen (1771-1858) is regarded as the father of the cooperative movement. He was a Welshman and made his mark in the cotton trade, Owen believed that keeping his workers in a good environment and giving access of education for their children would be worthy. This idea worked successfully in the cotton mills of New Lanark, Scotland. There the first co-operative store was opened. Also, he had the idea of forming "villages of co-operation" where workers would drag themselves out of poverty by growing their own food, making their own clothes and ultimately becoming self-governing.

William King: Owen inspired co-operative movement, but others - such as Dr. William King (1786-1865) - the adoption of his ideas and make them more effective and practical. King believed in starting small and working class realized that they would need to set up the cooperative, so that he saw his role as one of the directions. He thought of the cooperative philosophy and given practical advice about running a store that uses a mixture of the first edition of which appeared in the Co-operators.

The English CWS and Co-operative Group

The Co-operative Group formed gradually over 140 years from the merger of many independent retail societies, and their wholesale societies and federations. In 1863, twenty years after the Rochdale Pioneers opened their co-operative, the North of England Co-operative Society was launched by 300 individuals across Yorkshire and Lancashire. By 1872, it had become known as the Co-operative Wholesale Society (CWS). Through in the 20th century, smaller societies merged with CWS, such as the Scottish Co-operative Wholesale Society (1973) and the South Suburban Co-operative Society (1984).

Cooperative model was independently prepared by Raiffeisen and Schultz-Delitsch in Germany, and the credit union was developed simultaneously. The model was adopted by the United States by 1910. Although the first co-operative was formed in the United States during 1790s and it has a long history. By 1880, the member-owned organizations started to promote labor profitability. In the meanwhile, different kinds of co-operatives have been established and agriculture, wholesale purchasing, telephone, have continued to perform successfully in different regions, and consumers in the purchase of food.

Co-Operatives today: the Transition

Following Rochdale Co-operatives were formed, and an international association was formed in 1895. Co-operative enterprises became widespread, one of the largest and most successful examples being the industrial Mondragón Cooperative Corporation⁶ in the Basque country of Spain. Mondragon Co-op was founded under the oppressive conditions of Fascist Franco Spain after community-based democracy-building activities of a priest, Jose Maria Arizmendiarieta. They have become an extremely diverse network of co-operative enterprises, a huge enterprise in Spain, and a multinational concern. Co-operatives were also successful in Yugoslavia under Tito where Workers' Councils gained a significant role in management.

In many countries in Europe, cooperative institutions, retail banking and insurance businesses have a predominant market share, viz. 136 Initiative of Greece by such common products as concrete proposals for co-operation. In UK, Co-operatives and Co-Ops members of parliament representing the Co-operative Party, formed in the early 20th century. Co-operative Party, the Labour Party now has a permanent electoral agreement, and some Labour MPs, members of the Co-operative Party. UK retail food co-operatives in many parts of the country, insurance, banks, funeral services, and tourism industries retain a significant market share. Denmark also possess a strong background of cooperative movement. After World War II, the rebuilding of Germany was significantly determined by co-operative movement. Italian strong co-operative traditions resisted Cold War interference by US agencies. Co-

⁶ WIKIPEDIA. (2014, September 10). *Cooperative movement in India*. Retrieved October 14, 2015, from WIKIPEDIA: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cooperative_movement_in_India.

operative Bank was very successful throughout Europe. Danish wind power renewable energy co-operatives in Europe from 1970 became the first in the development.

Citizens' group of wind turbines operating in the various countries to begin to create alternative energy monopolies to social entrepreneurs co-deregulation of electricity markets by 1995, the UK began a broad ownership of the community involved. Where a large percentage of power is generated by nuclear sources in France, air power started in 2000 as supplementary source of energy. In Spain, the air power was developed by corporate-led effort, and it established a renewable energy that has focused on social enterprises to move further. Europe is almost similar to the Renewable Energy Co-Operatives that have been organized into a network.

In Asia some co-operative models are most successful in the world. However, traditional inequalities and the crisis somehow decreased in civil society in Asian countries such as South Korea, Japan, Philippines, Thailand etc. Originally founded in 1919, the International Labour Organization is actually a co-operative organisation in its structure laws etc. In Latin America the cooperative system as found in Brazil, Argentina was created in response to tackle the crisis based situation.

In Venezuela, Hugo Chavez's administration has of late resulted rapid and comprehensive development as co-operatives began to incentivize. As discussed earlier, in the Factory, labor union, employees' association and even among the farmhouses, there has a long history of Co-operative model since 1790s in United States. It has evolved with time. In Colorado, United Meadowlark cooperative provide facilities to the buyers and sellers land. In New York City, a variety of food cooperatives, since 1970, exists, and to add to those some new ones were established around 2010.

By 1908 Credit unions started to establish in the U.S. The member-owned co-operative structure created by such stable governance, was actually very slightly affected by the 2008 mortgage securities crisis. In US, Rural electric co-operatives were in the position from 1930; they became important economic strategy and were working successfully over the years. To demonstrate a progressive social and environmental consciousness, the position of the majority of the population was to value the cooperative initiative to continue with the renewable energy, and to decrease maximum use of the fossil fuel. And thus, a new generation of renewable energy has begun to organize cooperatives. In the United States agricultural cooperative also gained success. The United States, with over \$ 652 billion in annual revenue is generated in the co-operatives and above 2 million people is employed. One co-operative association was formed in 1920. There are over 29,000 cooperatives established. Co-Operatives are to meet the need for an organization. Meanwhile, US Federation of Worker Cooperatives was established in 20007.

Cooperatives Banks in India

In India, there are a number of banks who provide almost all kind of services that any individual requires. But in most cases, these banks that the people use are either private (that makes up a major part of banks) or nationalised banks. However, there is another kind of banks that are used by a large number of lower and middle class individuals of our society - co-operative banks. Although Co-operative banks are small-sized units and

⁷ WIKIPEDIA. (2015, November 02). *History of the cooperative movement*. Retrieved January 04, 2015, from WIKIPEDIA: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_the_cooperative_movement

organized both in urban and non-urban parts of this country, truly speaking, these banks are orthodox in nature and are centered around various clans, vicinities and work-groups and they mostly lend to small borrowers and businesses of the marginalised societies .

Basically situated in non-rural areas, the term Urban Co-operative Banks (UCBs), refers to primary cooperative banks which are located in comparatively developed areas where basic amenities at least available. These banks, until 1996, could only lend for non-agricultural purposes⁸.

However, today this sanction is no longer in effect. While the co-operative banks in rural areas basically provide loans and advances in agricultural based activities including farming, piggery, goatery, bovine-dairy, hatchery, sericulture, aquaculture etc. along with some small scale and cottage industries and self-employment encouraging activities, the co-operative banks in urban areas mainly finance various categories of people for self-employment including manufacturing and services sectors, e.g. medium and small scale manufacturing units, transport finance and home loan for residential purpose.

This may be mentioned that co-operative banks in India also are registered under the Co-operative Societies Act. All the cooperative banks are regulated by the Reserve Bank of India. They are governed by the Banking Regulations Act 1949 and Banking Laws (Co-operative Societies) Act, 1965.

⁸ Rediff.com. (2009, July 29). *What you need to know about co-operative banks*. Retrieved January 13, 2016, from Rediff.com: <http://www.rediff.com/money/report/perfi n-what-you-need-to-know-about-co-operative-banks/20090729.htm>

These banks provide all kind of monetary services such as opening of savings and current accounts, issuance of safe deposit lockers, providing loan or mortgages to private and business customers. ATM cards are among the new services of these banks. Some of the Co-Operative Banks in India even provide Internet Banking and Mobile Banking to attract more and more customers.

The co-operative banking structure in India, as we generally find, is divided into following main 5 categories:

Primary Urban Co-op Banks

Primary Agricultural Credit Societies

District Central Co-op Banks

State Co-operative Banks

Land Development Banks

Co-operative banks function on the basis of 'no-profit no-loss'. This is their main theme. Because the nature of these Co-operative banks, as a principle, is not to pursue the goal of profit maximisation. Therefore, some of these banks do not focus on offering more than the basic banking services. So, the prerogative of co-operative banks is based on financing small and marginalised borrowers in industrial and trade sectors, besides professional and salary classes who have fixed income. All these efforts are to minimise the risk of unsecured nature of loan. However, in India some cooperative banks are more positive than many of the nationalised and private sector banks as far as providing finance and recovery of outstanding overdue is concerned.

The total deposits and advances of cooperative banks in India is much higher, according to NAFCUB (National Federation of Urban Co-operative Banks and Credit Societies Ltd), than old private sector banks and also some new public sector banks. This exponential growth of co-operative banks in

India is because of mainly to their much better acquaintance of local people, greater interaction with customers, and their ability to catch the pulse of the local customers by providing extended service to them.

Although it is evident that the co-operative banks are not better than private banks in terms of facilities offered, their interest rates are certainly competitive. For example, often the interest rates on deposit are higher than nationalised and private banks and the interest rates on business and transport loans are often lower than that offered by private banks. However, unlike private banks, the documentation process is lengthy and getting a loan approved quickly is not always possible. Because the loans are mainly sanctioned by the Board of Directors and unlike nationalised banks the branch officials are not equipped with power of sanctioning any Long term loan or transaction loan especially if mortgage of property is associated with that particular loan. Although, the criteria for getting a loan from a UCB are more easier than for a loan from a commercial bank at times, for instance, while taking a house building loan, it does not matter whether the salary account is existing in the particular Co-Operative bank or not.

So, it makes better sense to have banking relationship with Urban Co-operative Banks today, because of the interest rates on deposit and advances some of them offer being the best in the industry. And also, with the danger of a run being minimised, they are surely on an equivalent footing with private and commercial banks when it comes to competing for customer's attention. However, to avail financial assistance, one has to be a member of the bank: own its shares worth at least 2.5 per cent (as per bye-law) of the loan amount, or a maximum of Rs.20,000 to Rs.25,000, varying on the bye-laws of the particular co-operative bank. This amount yields a return of 12-20 per cent in the form of yearly dividend based on the profit generated in a particular financial year. (Rediff.com, 2009)

- The rural cooperatives are divided into three kinds of Co-operatives Financial institutions.
- State Cooperative Banks- They operate at the apex level in states, the complete state comes as their area of operation
- District Central Cooperative Banks- They operate at the particular district only
- Primary Agricultural Credit Societies (PACS)-They operate at the village or grass-root level, the basic motto is to provide financial support to the farmers regarding cultivation
- The rural banking cooperatives are having quite a complex kind of monitoring structure because they have a dual control in turn that often yields many problems. State Level Task Force on Cooperative Urban Banks (TAFUCB), a Forum, has been established to look into various issues associated to duality in control:
- Banking activities are regulated by RBI and NABARD.
- Management and registration activities are managed by RCS (Registrar of Co-Operative Societies).
- Land Developmental Banks are basically set up to develop the agricultural productivity of land. Financial help to the farmers in order to facilitate them with modern technologies is the motto of this kind of Bank. Land development banks provide long-term advances for various agriculture related projects apart from development of land and land related business. The borrowing capacity of a member is generally fixed according to the holding of his share number in the bank. The loan is granted by land development bank is to be repaid within 20 to 30 years. In most cases, loans are granted up to 50% of the valuation of the land or up to 30 times the revenue generated. Loans are sanctioned after a thorough verification and scrutinisation of

security title-deeds as per the requirement of the loan. The rates of interest for Long Term loans are generally low and within the paying capacity of agriculturists. They are around 11 to 12% as per the provision of the particular Land Developmental Bank⁹.

- Co-Operative credit society is commonly known as the primary agricultural credit society; it is the basic structure of co-operative credit. It has direct interaction with farmer borrowers, for granting short and medium term loans and also to facilitate distribution and marketing aspects. The major objective of the co-operative development programmes is to ensure that the benefits of co-operative activities flow increasingly to weaker sections, including scheduled castes and scheduled tribes (Kameswari, 2011, June).
- Marketing co-operatives have an instrumental role to play in the concept of inclusive growth, because these co-operatives are directly concerned with improving livelihood in rural areas. Marketing co-operatives ensures a remunerative price to the cultivator, sellers by streamlining the age-old system of agricultural marketing. For this to be possible however, these Co-Operatives must overcome their functional and managerial constraints (Singh, 2007, October).

⁹ WIKIPEDIA. (2014, March 11). *Land development bank*. Retrieved January 13, 2016, from WIKIPEDIA: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Land_development_bank

Significance of Co-Operative

A co-operative in a vast country like India is of great significance because:

A co-operative is an organization for the poor, marginalised, illiterate and unskilled people it actually gather the have-nots together and boost them to move forward with a common goal It is an institution for mutual help and sharing among the people of equal standard

It reduces class conflicts and social disparities; rich and poor both get come together under a single umbrella and to discuss about future prospects

It reduces the bureaucratic red-tape-ism and malfunctioning the laws are much more simpler than Corporate laws and Government laws

It can put new efforts to overcomes the constraints of development in all the the the sectors, viz. agricultural, manufacturing and service sector

It creates conducive environment for cottage industries in rural sector all round the world where even smaller artisans get their fare share of opportunities

Causes of Slow Progress

Despite rapid growth the overall progress of co-operative movement during 100 years of its existence is not very impressive. It is therefore necessary to know the causes of poor performance of the movement and on that basis take such steps as would promote a faster growth of Co-Operative movement in India.

- Government Interference: The co-operative movement in India was initiated in 1904 under the rule of British government. Since then the govt has adopted an attitude of

patronizing the movement. After attainment of independence also, quite often co-operative societies are imposed upon the people, thus the spirit of cooperation cannot flower fully in these circumstances. Hence, It just grew very slowly and that too haphazardly.

- Bureaucracy and politicisation: Introduction of Bureaucratic Management system through incorporation of IAS officers as Principal Secretary of Centre & State Governments and as Chairmen of Co-operative service Commissions has become institutionalised. And, according to bye-laws, all co-operative structures necessarily have to have election to form Board of Directors; thus political predominance of vested interests resulting in non-percolation of benefits to a common member, particularly to the class of persons for whom such co-operatives were basically formed, has also retarded the development of co-operatives. Hence, bureaucratic control and interference in the management, political interference and over-politicisation have proved harmful to their growth. These are the areas which need to be attended to by evolving suitable legislative and policy support.
- Marginal people avoided: The failure of co-operatives in the country is mainly attributable to dormant membership and lack of active participation of members in the management of co-operatives. Also, the majority of the members are from affluent society, i.e., rich people represent the co-operatives while marginal people's participation is mostly avoided. Mounting over-dues in co-operatives credit institutions, lack of mobilisation of internal resources and over-dependence on government assistance, lack of professional management.
- Mismanagement and manipulation: Over the years, this truly democratic idea got corrupted in co-operatives and the system became fragile to a large extent. In agricultural co-operatives, farmers with larger holdings grew more powerful. In practice, this altered the power structure of the co-operatives. In the elections to the governing bodies of the co-operatives, money often became such a powerful tool that the top posts of chairman and vice-chairman usually went to the richest farmers even though the majority of members were farmers with small- or medium-sized holdings.
- Lack of Awareness: Even today, poor people are not well informed about the objectives of the co-operative movement. Unfortunately, no special efforts were put into this as yet. People look upon these institutions as means for gathering facilities and concessions from the govt.; hence, most people expect to get co-operatives as means of receiving subsidy from the government.
- Restricted Coverage: Most of these societies are confined to a few members and their operations are restricted into small area. As a result their resources remain limited, which makes it impossible for them to expand. Also, the most of the societies are created with single motto. For this reason these societies are unable to take a comprehensive view of a particular problem and thus remain unable to solve it completely.
- Functional Weakness: The co-operative movement has suffered from inadequacy of trained personnel right from its inception. Often it is found that the need of the member has not been properly assessed before providing credit support. Also the credit worthiness is of the

member is overlooked at times. Thus the repayment aspect gets adversely affected and in turn the co-operative gets affected and at times they face severe loss also. (Das, 2006)

Conclusion

After age old transformations, co-operatives have still been evolving. The picture is not as bright as it should have been. But it is quite evident that this concept is one of the most tested and trusted method of community development where the profit can be shared by a huge number of people in order to get optimum result leading to qualitative improvement of both social and economic lifestyle of the beneficiaries.

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